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THE ROLE OF THE CLASS TEACHER IN THE PROCESS OF INTEGRATING MIGRANTS' CHILDREN INTO THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The article addresses the current issue of the role of the class teacher in ensuring the integration of migrant children in the modern Russian school. The class teacher is a key figure in recognizing the equality of all subjects and participants in the educational process. The class teacher acts as a mediator in building relationships between students, teachers, and parents; as a creator of an optimal developmental microenvironment and a favorable moral and psychological climate in the classroom.*

Key words: *multicultural education, migrant children, class teacher, polyethnic competence.*

The dynamic changes that have taken place in the life of modern society over the past decade have led to the gradual transformation of the Russian school into a multicultural educational space. Multicultural education involves "the formation of a person capable of active and effective functioning in a multinational and multicultural environment, possessing a developed sense of understanding and respect for other cultures, and the ability to live in peace and harmony with people of different nationalities, races, and beliefs" [1].

The problem of a multicultural environment in an educational institution has an integrative nature and is studied in the context of pedagogy, psychology, philosophy, cultural studies, sociology, and other sciences. One of the important principles of multicultural education is that the student acts as an active subject within this environment. However, a student can only become an active subject by interacting with the environment under the guidance of teachers, who create conditions for the student's active involvement in school life and society as a whole.

Let's take a closer look at the impact of a multicultural educational environment on the personal development and adaptation of students from migrant families. It is advisable to assess changes based on two levels of group and personal development. Group development includes the role and status position in the group, the ability to build new relationships in multicultural groups, taking into account the duration of interaction with various subjects (constant or situational), the degree of involvement in the educational process and joint activities, the presence of migrantophobia in the educational institution and its prevalence, and the degree of adaptation of migrant children in the school and the country as a whole. Such an assessment of the educational environment dictates the need to develop a system of social interaction between various institutions (educational and social services), migrant parents, and the indigenous population in order to effectively adapt students to the new conditions of their education, upbringing, and professional development.

The group level of development is closely related to the individual level. The successful adaptation of migrant students in a multicultural educational environment depends on the psychological state and mood of the students (both migrants and the local population) and the teaching staff. Adaptation to a different country and cultural environment is accompanied by various stressful situations that can lead to psychological instability, frustration, fear, and aggression, which can pose a psychological and pedagogical risk for migrant students. In cases of prolonged adaptation or maladaptation, personality changes manifest themselves in extreme forms, such as pronounced aggressive behavior (especially towards peers in the host country), uncontrollable behavior, extremism, and even hatred towards the host population, teachers, and classmates, or apathy and depression.

The social situation of forced migration has the greatest negative impact on children's mental development. Psychologists identify the following psychological characteristics of children from families of forced migrants. Since forced migration is often caused by military conflicts and aggressive actions in their home countries, children are prone to post-traumatic stress disorder, fears, neuroses, and repressed aggression. However, even without the situation of forced migration, migrant children exhibit high levels of anxiety and fear. Researchers working in the field of studying the behavior of migrants describe the phenomenon of "cultural shock" caused by socio-cultural adaptation to other living conditions, another culture. Against this background, there is a cultural "duality", a conflict of values. Almost all migrant children are characterized by a sense of loss, depression, loss of "home" and a sense of security associated with it. As a rule, most children from migrant families have pedagogical neglect, they are often not ready for school, and school-age children do not have the skills to read in Russian (or they are insufficient to study in a Russian-speaking school).

Older students are not ready to make their professional choices and are not ready to enter professional educational institutions [3]. Many researchers note the high level of psychoemotional stress in migrant families, as well as the psychological problems faced by parents due to financial and social issues. Thus, migrant children become a category of children at risk due to many factors: pedagogical (they are not ready or capable of acquiring educational and personal competencies), psychological (they have various cognitive, emotional, and behavioral disorders that are not related to organic brain disorders), and socio-psychological (they are involved in interethnic conflicts and adaptation risks).

Students from families of forced migrants should be under special control of social and psychological services and school psychologists, as they have experienced traumatic effects and are therefore at risk. Multicultural education should address the challenges of students living at the crossroads of different cultures (ethnic identity and its preservation), promoting gradual integration rather than exacerbating them by forcing development. To create a nurturing environment, it is essential to foster an atmosphere of acceptance and respect for the cultures of different ethnic groups, rather than rejecting or denying the values of other nations.

The multifaceted development of an individual in a multicultural educational environment is impossible without recognizing the equal value and rights of all ethnic and social groups. In the educational environment, as well as in society as a whole, discrimination based on nationality, religion, gender, or age is unacceptable. The educational environment is essential for individuals to understand their own roots and place in life and society. It should foster respect for other cultures, create a diverse worldview, and promote effective adaptation in a changing and multi-ethnic society. The basis of a developing environment in multicultural education is cultural diversity, acceptance, integration of culture and traditions into education, cultural and ethnic identity, and psychological and pedagogical support for these processes.

This situation creates additional difficulties for school teachers, who, in addition to their main functions, have to regulate the interaction between children and parents of different nationalities. The class teacher acts as a mediator in building relationships between students, teachers, and parents, and creates an optimal developing microenvironment and a favorable moral and psychological climate in the classroom. The class teacher is a key figure in recognizing the parity of all subjects and participants in the educational process. The current situation exacerbates the contradiction between the current level of professional and pedagogical training of modern teachers and the requirements for them as class teachers in a changing multicultural educational environment.

We have found that the requirement for the multicultural competence of a class teacher is not specified in the practice of modern schools. Polyethnic competence is an integrative quality of an individual that includes a system of multicultural knowledge, skills, interests, needs, motives, values, multicultural qualities, experience, social norms, and rules of behavior necessary for everyday life and activity in a multicultural society, which is realized in the ability to solve professional tasks through positive interaction with representatives of different cultures.

The expediency of highlighting the polyethnic competence in the structure of a teacher's professional competence as a class teacher is primarily due to the need for a more precise and meaningful definition of the teacher's personal qualities, professional knowledge, and skills necessary for successful teaching in a multicultural environment.

In our opinion, the polyethnic competence of a class teacher involves knowledge of the history of other nationalities, cultural characteristics of peoples, respect for them, and the opportunity to learn the best from other cultures; the ability to engage in intercultural dialogue in order to understand each other and achieve mutual recognition. However, many class teachers lack sufficient professional knowledge to ensure the psychological safety of students.

According to some modern researchers, the multi-ethnic competence of a modern teacher who performs the functions of a class teacher is of great professional importance. It is especially important for a class teacher to be able to correctly understand the cultural, ethnic, and national differences between students and their families, and to be able to promote cultural pluralism in society through their personal actions and words [4].

The specificity of the professional competence of a class teacher in a multi-ethnic school lies in the development of their competencies to a level that is sufficient to perform their professional duties in the specific conditions of a multi-ethnic student body. Multi-ethnic competence is a personal quality of a modern teacher that encompasses a set of values and attitudes, a willingness to embrace other cultures, an understanding and acceptance of the multidimensional nature of the world, and a readiness to work in a multicultural educational environment.

The structure of multi-ethnic competence includes its components, which, in the modern interpretation, are present in the meaningful construct of multicultural competence: understanding the uniqueness and value of other peoples and cultures; a tolerant model of behavior; cultural tolerance and ethnic identity; a way of individual existence in the field of ethno-cultural dissonances; and the creative realization of the self in culturally appropriate ways of understanding the world [2].

The expediency of highlighting the multicultural competence in the structure of a teacher's professional competence is due to the need, firstly, for a more precise definition and substantive interpretation of the personal qualities, professional knowledge, and skills necessary for successful teaching in a multicultural environment, and secondly, for developing a program to improve the system of professional and pedagogical training for teachers in the context of modern socio-pedagogical realities.

Considering the polyethnic competence in relation to the activities of a class teacher, we believe that there are three most significant components in its structure: the motivational and value component, the communicative component, and the socio-perceptive component.

The motivational and value component contributes to the creation of conditions for the functioning of abilities and the inclusion of the class teacher's orientation towards the content of students' inner world and their interest in learning about the Other, as well as their awareness of their personal and professional positions. It includes the following characteristics: focus on another person; need for communication; and self-representation in the professional world.

The communicative component is defined as a set of skills and abilities of the class teacher that ensure his interaction with students and the effective solution of various communication tasks. The communicative component in the structure of the class teacher's socio-psychological competence includes the following characteristics: regulating interpersonal relationships between students in the class; establishing effective interaction between subject teachers and students; and promoting a positive psychological climate in the class.

The socio-perceptive component implies that the class teacher is ready to have an unconditional, non-evaluative, and positive perception of the students in their class. In addition, the socio-perceptive component manifests itself in the high and flexible self-esteem of the class teacher, the optimal level of anxiety, and the adequate expression of their emotions.

Thus, the polyethnic competence of a class teacher is a complex formation characterized by its unique structure, content, and quality characteristics. It should be noted that the success of a class teacher's work depends on the development of all three components to the same extent.

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